

REVIEW ON BUCCAL PATCH AS A MUCOSAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

A Buccal drug delivery system is a method of administering drugs through the buccal mucosa (the inner lining of the cheek), where the drug is absorbed directly into the systemic circulation. The buccal patch, formulated in a matrix design, comprises a mixture of the drug, adhesive, and various additives. Bidirectional patches deliver the drug to both the mucosal surface and into the oral cavity. The patch consists of one or more layers of polymer films that contain the drug and other excipients. A buccal patch is a thin, non-dissolving matrix designed for modified-release medication. The buccal mucosa acts as a lipoidal barrier to drug passage, similar to many other mucosal membranes, and the absorption of a drug molecule becomes easier as its lipophilicity increases. Bypassing the first-pass hepatic metabolism and entering the systemic circulation directly through the jugular vein, the buccal route of drug delivery offers high bioavailability. Additionally, buccal delivery ensures patient compliance, provides a painless alternative to injections, and supports both local and systemic therapeutic effects.

KEY WORDS:

Buccal drug delivery, systemic circulation , first pass metabolism ,oral cavity, buccal mucosa, and drug permeability.

1.INTRODUCTION

Among the different drug delivery methods, the oral route is arguably the one that both patients and doctors prefer. However, there are drawbacks to oral drug administration, including hepatic first pass metabolism and GI tract enzymatic degradation, which make it impossible to administer some drug classes—particularly peptides and proteins—orally. As a result, additional absorptive mucosae are thought to be possible drug administration sites.⁽¹⁾

Conversely, mucosal layers (oral, rectal, vaginal, ocular, and nasal) are frequently regarded as possible drug administration sites and offer clear benefits for systemic drug delivery. The potential liver bypass effect and the avoidance of presystemic elimination in the GI tract, along with enhanced absorption and consequently improved bioavailability, are some of these benefits.⁽²⁾

There are more uses for mucoadhesive polymers in buccal drug delivery. Recent years have seen the development of numerous mucoadhesive devices, such as tablets, films, patches, disks, strips, ointments, and gels. But compared to the other devices, the buccal patch offers more comfort and flexibility. Furthermore, because oral gels are readily removed by saliva, a patch can get around the issue of their comparatively brief residence time on mucosa. Bypassing the first pass hepatic metabolism and entering the systemic circulation directly through the jugular vein, the buccal route of drug delivery offers high bioavailability.

1.1.Buccal drug delivery system :

A delivery mechanism intended for the systemic or local administration of drugs through the buccal mucosa. Buccal delivery refers to the release of the drug that happens when a dosage form is positioned in the outer vestibule between the buccal mucosa and the gum.⁽³⁾

Buccal dosage form :**❖ Buccal mucoadhesive tablets :**

Buccal mucoadhesive tablets are solid dosage forms that need to be moistened before they are placed in contact with the buccal mucosa. For instance, a double-layer tablet is made up of an adhesive matrix layer consisting of hydroxyl propyl cellulose and polyacrylic acid, with an inner core of cocoa butter that contains insulin and a penetration enhancer (sodium glycocholate).

Patches and film :

Buccal patches are composed of two layers, where a solution of the adhesive polymer is applied onto a non-permeable backing sheet, which is subsequently cut into the desired oval shape. A new mucosal adhesive film named “Zilactin”—made from an alcoholic solution of hydroxy propyl cellulose and three organic acids. This film, when applied to the oral mucosa, can remain in position for a minimum of 12 hours, even when exposed to liquids.⁽⁴⁾

Buccal patches :

Patch consists of one or more layers of polymer films that contain the drug and other excipients. A buccal patch is a thin, non-dissolving matrix designed for modified-release medication.⁽⁵⁾

It may include a mucoadhesive polymer layer that adheres to the oral mucosa, gums, or teeth, facilitating controlled drug release into the oral mucosa (unidirectional release), the oral cavity (unidirectional release), or both (bidirectional release). After a designated period, the patch is removed from the mouth and discarded.⁽⁶⁾

Eg: Nicotine, lidocaine, propranolol, atenolol

1.2. ORAL CAVITY:**❖ Anatomic and physiologic features :**

The oral mucosa, covering an area of 170 cm², has a structure composed of three distinct layers: the epithelium, the lamina propria, and the submucosa. The protective buccal epithelial layer is divided into two types: the flexible non-keratinized mucosa that lines the soft palate, the underside of the tongue, sublingual mucosa, the floor of the oral cavity, the

inner lips, and the buccal pouch, and the keratinized mucosa that covers the hard palate, gingiva, and the dorsal side of the tongue within the oral cavity.⁽⁷⁾

A schematic illustration highlighting key regions of the buccal area is included. Numerous textbooks and reference materials offer comprehensive discussions on the essential anatomical and physiological aspects of the oral cavity, as well as the teeth, tongue, salivary glands and orofacial muscles.

Figure no:1.1 A schematic diagram depicting the key regions of the buccal area

1.3.Bioadhesion:

A 'bioadhesive' refers to a material that can interact with biological substances and be retained on them or bind them together for a prolonged duration. Bioadhesives are categorized into three types

- 1) The first type involves bioadhesion between biological layers that does not include artificial materials; examples include cell diffusion and cell aggregation
- 2) The second type encompasses bioadhesion observed with cell adhering to culture dishes or sticking to a variety of materials including metals, wood and various synthetic substance.
- 3) The third type pertains to the adhesion of artificial materials to biological substrates, such as the bonding of polymers to skin or other soft tissues.⁽⁸⁾

1.3.1 Mechanism of bioadhesion :

To achieve bioadhesion, three stages must be involved:

- 1) A close interaction occurs between a bioadhesive and a membrane, either due to effective wetting of the bioadhesive on the membrane or because of the bioadhesive's swelling.
- 2) The bioadhesive infiltrates into the tissue.

The polymer chains of the bioadhesive interlace with the mucous, allowing for the formation of weak chemical bonds.

1.3.2.Theories of bioadhesion or mucoadhesion :

Several theories have been proposed to explain the fundamental mechanism of adhesion.

A) Wetting theory :

Wetting theory primarily pertains to liquid bioadhesive systems, examining adhesive and contact behavior as a liquid or paste disperses over a biological system. The work of adhesion, defined in terms of surface and interfacial tension, is represented as energy per cm^2 released when an interface is created. According to Dupres' equation, the work of adhesion is expressed as $W_A = \gamma_{AB} - \gamma_A - \gamma_B$, where A represents the biological membrane and B denotes the bioadhesive formulation. The work of cohesion can be expressed as $\gamma_{Wc} = \gamma_B - 2\gamma_A$. For a bioadhesive material B to spread on a biological substrate, the spreading coefficient is defined as $\gamma_{SB/A} = \gamma_{AB} + \gamma_A - \gamma_B$. The spreading coefficient ($\gamma_{SB/A}$) needs to be positive for a bioadhesive material to successfully adhere to a biological membrane.

In the case of a bioadhesive liquid B sticking to a biological membrane A, the contact angle is represented by,⁽⁹⁾

$$\cos(\varphi_{AB}) = \cos(\varphi)$$

B)Diffusion theory :

Based on this theory, the polymer chains intermingle with the mucus to a sufficient extent, forming a semi-permanent adhesive connection. The specific depth to which the polymer chains infiltrate the mucus is influenced by the diffusion coefficient and the duration of contact. This diffusion coefficient is also reliant on the molecular weight between cross-links

and considerably diminishes as the cross-linking density decreases. Additional interactions occur between the mucoadhesive device and the mucus.⁽¹⁰⁾

C) Electronic theory :

As per this theory, electronic transfer takes place when an adhesive polymer comes into contact with the mucus glycoprotein network, due to variations in their electronic structures. This leads to the creation of an electronic double layer at the interface, and adhesion occurs because of attractive forces within the double layer.

D) Fracture theory :

Based on fracture theory, adhesion involves the separation of two surface following their bonding. The adhesive strength is represented by the fracture strength as expressed by the formula

$$G = (E\varepsilon / L)^{1/2}.$$

Where: E= Young's module of elasticity ε = Fracture energy L= Critical crack length when two surfaces are separated.

E) Adsorption theory :

This theory suggests that when two surfaces first come into contact, they stick due to the surface forces at play between the atoms in both materials. The adsorption process involves two categories of chemical bonds: primary covalent bonds (which are permanent) and secondary chemical bonds (which encompass electrostatic forces, van der Waals forces, as well as hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds).⁽¹¹⁾

Mechanism of buccal absorption :

Buccal drug absorption takes place through the passive diffusion of nonionized species, primarily influenced by a concentration gradient, as they move through the epithelial intercellular spaces. The main method of transport for non-ionic species across the lipid membrane of the buccal cavity is passive transport. The buccal mucosa acts as a lipoidal barrier to drug passage, similar to many other mucosal membranes, and the absorption of a drug molecule becomes easier as its lipophilicity increases. The buccal absorption dynamics

of drugs can be effectively explained by a first-order rate process. Several obstacles to buccal drug absorption have been recognized. Dearden and Tomlison (1971) noted that salivary secretion affects the kinetics of buccal absorption from drug solutions by altering the drug concentration in the oral cavity. The relationship between salivary secretion and time is expressed as follows.⁽¹²⁾

$$- dm/dt = Kc/ViV$$

Where,

M - Mass of drug in mouth at time t_1

K - Proportionality constant

C - Concentration of drug in mouth at time

V_i - The volume of solution put into mouth cavity and V_t - Salivary secretion rate Factors affecting

2.Types of buccal patches

a) Matrix type (Bi-directional):

The buccal patch, formulated in a matrix design, comprises a mixture of the drug, adhesive, and various additives. Bidirectional patches deliver the drug to both the mucosal surface and into the oral cavity.

Figure no:2.1 Buccal patch designed for bidirectional drug release

b) Reservoir type (Unidirectional):

The buccal patch created as a reservoir system includes a compartment for the medication and other components distinct from the adhesive. An impermeable backing is utilized to manage the route of drug delivery, minimize patch deformation and disintegration in the mouth, and prevent medication loss. Essentially, unidirectional buccal patches are employed for drug delivery within the buccal cavity for both local and systemic effects.⁽¹³⁾

Figure no:2.2Buccal patch designed for unidirectional drug release

3.Composition of buccal patches**A. Active ingredient:**

The distribution of a range of APIs is possible with buccal film technology. Nevertheless, high dose molecules are challenging to put into buccal film due to the dosage form's size limitations. Typically, the buccal patches might include between 5%w/w and 30%w/w of active medicinal substances.

B. Polymers (adhesive layer):

Hydroxyethylcellulose, hydroxypropyl cellulose, polyvinyl pyrrolidone, polyvinyl alcohol, carbopol and other mucoadhesive polymers.

C. Diluents:

Lactose DC is chosen as a diluent due to its excellent solubility in water, flavoring qualities, and physical-mechanical characteristics that render it appropriate for direct compression. Another example includes microcrystalline starch and starch.

D. Sweetening agents:

Sucralose, aspartame, mannitol, etc.

E. Flavouring agents:

Menthol, vanillin, clove oil, etc.

F. Backing layer:

Ethyl cellulose, etc.

G. Penetration enhancer:

Cyano acrylate, etc.

H. Plasticizers:

PEG-100, 400, propylene glycol, etc⁽¹⁴⁾

4.Methods of preparation of buccal patches

1. Solvent casting
2. Direct milling
3. Solid dispersion extrusion
4. Semisolid casting
5. Hot melt extrusion

1. Solvent casting:

In this approach, all excipients for the patch, including the drug, are mixed in an organic solvent and applied to a sheet of release liner. After the solvent has evaporated, a thin layer of protective backing material is adhered to the coated release liner, creating a laminate that is then die-cut into patches of the required size and shape.

Figure no:4.1 Solvent casting method

2. Direct milling:

In this method, patches are produced without using solvents. The drug and excipients are mechanically blended through direct milling or kneading, typically without any liquid present. Once the mixing is complete, the resulting material is rolled onto a release liner until the desired thickness is reached. The backing material is then laminated as described earlier. Although there are only minor or no differences in performance between patches made using these two methods, the solvent-free approach is preferred due to the absence of residual solvents and the avoidance of related health concerns.

Figure no:4.2 Direct milling method

3. Solid dispersion extrusion:

In this technique, immiscible components are extruded with the drug, and solid dispersions are subsequently produced. Finally, these solid dispersions are formed into films using dies.

Figure no:4.3 Solid dispersion method

4. Semisolid casting:

In the semisolid casting technique, a solution of a water-soluble film-forming polymer is initially prepared. This solution is then combined with a solution of an acid-insoluble polymer (such as cellulose acetate phthalate or cellulose acetate butyrate), which has been prepared in ammonium or sodium hydroxide. An appropriate quantity of plasticizer is then added to create a gel mass. Ultimately, this gel mass is cast into films or ribbons utilizing heat-controlled drums. The film thickness is typically between 0.015 and 0.05 inches. The ratio of the acid-insoluble forming polymer should be

Figure no:4.4 Semisolid casting method

5. Hot melt extrusion:

In the hot melt extrusion process, the drug is initially blended with carriers in their solid state. Next, the extruder equipped with heaters melts the mixture. Finally, the molten material is shaped into films using dies. The hot melt extrusion method offers several advantages, including fewer operational units, improved content uniformity, and a process that does not require water.⁽¹⁵⁾

Figure no:4.5 Hot melt extrusion method

5. Evaluation of buccal patches:

The following tests are used to evaluate the Buccal Patches:

1. Weight consistency:

The weight variation is assessed by weighing five randomly chosen patches from each batch.

2. Thickness consistency:

Each patch's thickness is measured at five distinct points using digital vernier calipers, and the average thickness is determined.

3. Folding durability

The folding durability of each patch is evaluated by folding it repeatedly at the same point until it either breaks or is folded up to 300 times, which is deemed adequate to demonstrate favorable film characteristics.

4. Surface pH measurement:

The prepared buccal patches are allowed to swell for two hours on the surface of an agar plate, which is made by mixing 2% (w/v) agar in warm phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 while stirring, and then pouring the mixture into a Petri dish to gel at room temperature. The surface pH is measured by placing pH paper on the surface of the swollen patch, and the average of three readings is recorded.

5. Drug content consistency:

To assess drug content consistency, a 3 cm patch (without the backing membrane) is individually dissolved in a mixture of 100 ml of ethanol and simulated saliva solution (pH 6.2) in a ratio of 20:80 for 12 hours with occasional shaking. The resulting solution is filtered, and the drug content is quantified spectrophotometrically, with the average from three measurements being taken.

6. Swelling ratio:

Individual buccal patches are weighed (W_1) and placed in separate petri dishes filled with phosphate buffer at pH 6.8. After soaking, the patches are taken out and excess surface water is blotted off with filter paper. The patches are then reweighed (W_2), and the swelling index (SI) is calculated using the formula: $SI = (W_2 - W_1) / W_1$.⁽¹⁶⁾

6. CONCLUSION

Mucoadhesive buccal patches have recently gained popularity for drug delivery. This review summarizes current research and highlights potential future directions for preparing mucoadhesive buccal patches with variety of polymers. The buccal mucosa provides advantages over controlled drug delivery for longer periods of time. The mucosa receives adequate vascular and lymphatic drainage, preventing first-pass metabolism in the liver and pre-systemic elimination in the gastrointestinal tract. The location seems to be acceptable to the patient and is ideal for a retentive device. It is possible to regulate and modify the mucosa's permeability and local environment to allow for drug penetration with the appropriate dosage form design and formulation.

For powerful medications with a quick onset of action, macromolecules, and vaccines, the highly vascularized and immunologically competent buccal mucosa can be thought of as a viable and alluring alternative delivery method. However, for the field of buccal drug delivery to advance quickly, safe and efficient penetration/absorption enhancers are required. This review posess the formulation and evaluation of various types of buccal patch.

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